

Three New Names in *Puya* (Bromeliaceae), *Sedum* (Crassulaceae) and *Yucca* (Asparagaceae)

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Abstract—New names are proposed for three taxa that lack a legitimate name at their currently accepted taxonomic position: *Puya ramosissima*, *Sedum pentandrellum* and *Yucca luminosa*.

Puya ramosissima auctt. ex M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. nov.** ≡ *Puya ramosa* L.B.Sm. (in [Phytologia 9: 250. 1963](#)), nom. illeg., non *Puya ramosa* J.St.-Hil. (in [Expos. Fam. Nat. 1: 123. 1805](#)).

Sedum pentandrellum M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. nov.** ≡ *Sedella pentandra* H.Sharsm. (in [Madroño 3: 240. 1936](#)) = “*Sedum pentandrum* (Sharsm.) ined.” ([POWO](#), retrieved 15 Mar 2024), non *Sedum pentandrum* (DC.) Boreau (in [Fl. Centre France, ed. 2: 205 n. 779. 1849](#)) [= *Sedum villosum* L.]. Etymology: Diminutive form of *pentandrum*, in reference to the generic name *Sedella*.

Yucca luminosa auctt. ex M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. et stat. nov.** ≡ *Yucca rupicola* var. *rigida* Engelm. (in [Trans. Acad. Sci. St. Louis 3: 49. 1873](#)) ≡ *Yucca rigida* (Engelm.) Trel. (in [Rep. \(Annual\) Missouri Bot. Gard. 13: 65. 1902](#)), nom. illeg., non *Yucca ×rigida* André (in [Rev. Hort. \[Paris\]. 55: 110. 1883](#)) [= *Yucca ×andreana* Deleuil ex André].

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